

APPLICATION OF SEVERE PLASTIC DEFORMATION TO PROCESS A W-CU NANOCOMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: A W-25%Cu coarse grained composite is subjected to high pressure torsion (HPT) at room temperature to different strains. The evolution of the microstructure of the material during HPT is studied. Inhomogeneous plastic deformation of the W-25%Cu is found at low strains ($\epsilon_{eq} < 16$): Localized deformation bands are visible in the microstructure. A strong tungsten fragmentation is observed after HPT to a higher strains. After HPT to a strain of 256, a very homogeneous microstructure with a tungsten particle size of 10-20nm is observed. The effect of the change of the deformation direction on the fragmentation process is considered.

KEYWORDS: high pressure torsion, W-Cu composite, particle fragmentation, nanocomposites.

INTRODUCTION

Coarse-grained W-Cu composites have been widely used in engineering for heavy-duty electrical contacts, heat sinks, arcing resistance electrodes, etc, as the tungsten's resistance to arc erosion is combined with copper's excellent electrical and thermal properties [1, 2]. Recently, a few attempts have been done to fabricate W-Cu nanocomposites [3, 4] since the nanomaterials can demonstrate unigual mechanical and physical properties [5, 6]. A standard procedure used to process a W-Cu nanocomposite consists of the following steps:

- 1) Fabrication of tungsten's and copper's nanopowder by (high energy) ball milling;
- 2) Their mixing and further compaction;
- 3) Sintering.

This procedure, however, has a few shortcomings which prevent a fabrication of a high-qualitative W-Cu nanocomposite. Firstly, impurities (such as iron, cobalt, etc.) are usually induced into nanopowders during their fabrication. These impurities significantly degrade the electrical properties of the material. Secondly, a full densification cannot be achieved in the material. And, thirdly, a significant grain growth can take place during the liquid-state sintering of the material [3, 4, 6]. It should be also noted that this fabrication process appears very time- and labour-consuming.

In this paper, we will present a new mode of fabrication of nanocomposite materials. It is applied to a W-Cu composite. In contrast to the standard method, nanoparticles are processed directly within already as-fabricated coarse-grained W-Cu composite by fragmentation of tungsten particles during high pressure torsion (HPT).

Fig. 1: The microstructure of the W-25%Cu in the as-fabricated condition

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

A material for this investigation is a W-25%Cu composite fabricated by PLANSEE (Reutte, Austria). The equiaxed tungsten particles have a size of 2 to 10 μm (Fig. 1a). It should be noted that the particles are inhomogeneously distributed within the copper matrix (Fig. 1b). The samples for HPT have a disk shape with a diameter of 8 mm and a thickness t of 0.8 mm (Fig. 2). Samples are deformed at a pressure of 8 GPa. The number of turns n is selected to attain a certain equivalent strain at radius r according to Eq. (1)

$$\varepsilon_{eq} = \frac{2\pi nr}{t\sqrt{3}}. \quad (1)$$

The samples are deformed by monotonous shear in one direction at room temperature to strains of 4, 16, 64, 256, and 512 at a radius of 3 mm. To study the effect of the change of the shear direction on the fragmentation process, samples are subjected to cyclic HPT:

- 1) To a strain of 32 in one direction plus to a strain of 32 in the opposite direction. Further, in the text, it is noted as 32x2 for short;
- 2) By a change of a shear direction four times after each deformation to a strain of 32 (or “32x4”, for short).

The evolution of microstructure during monotonous and cyclic HPT is investigated in detail by a scanning electron microscope.

After HPT, the samples are ground and polished. The microstructure is investigated on the transversal section (perpendicular to the shear plane) at a radius of 3 mm from the torsion axis (marked as shaded plane in Fig. 2) by a scanning electron microscope LEO 1525. The

Fig. 2: Schematical view of the sample for HPT

*Fig. 3. The microstructure of the W-25%Cu after HPT to a strain of:
a, b) 4; c) 16; d) 64; e) 256; f) 512*

tungsten particle size and other microstructural parameters are determined by a computer program “ANALYSIS”.

RESULTS

Fragmentation of tungsten during monotonous HPT

A slight deformation by shear of coarse-grained tungsten particles occurs at the beginning of HPT (Fig. 3a). Some localized deformation bands are visible, as well (Fig. 3b). Only a few tungsten particles are broken at this stage of deformation. As a rule, they are located within or nearby localized deformation bands. After HPT to a strain of 16, the fraction of broken tungsten particles and the density of deformation bands significantly increases (Fig. 3c). An increase of strain to 64 leads to a very inhomogeneous microstructure: A strong tungsten fragmentation takes place at this stage of deformation. Elongated tungsten particles with aspect ratios up to 20 aligned on angle of 0 to 30° to the shear plane (Fig. 3d) and very small equiaxed tungsten particles having a size between 20 -100 nm are observed. A further increase of strain to 256 leads to a very homogeneous microstructure with a particle size between 10 and 20 nm (Fig. 3e). The microstructure reaches a saturation at this stage of deformation, a further increase of strain does not change the microstructure. The microstructure of the sample deformed to a strain of 512 (Fig. 3f) looks very similar to the microstructure at $\epsilon_{eq} = 256$ (Fig. 3e).

Fragmentation of tungsten during cyclic HPT

The microstructure of the W-25%Cu after cyclic HPT to a strain of “32x2” (Fig. 4a) is different from the microstructure of the material after monotonous HPT to a strain of 64 (Fig. 3d), although the same value of strain is induced into both samples. It is visible that the fragmentation process proceeds more quicker during cyclic HPT in comparison with the monotonous HPT: The tungsten particles are significantly smaller after cyclic HPT compared to those after monotonous HPT. The cyclic HPT to a strain of “32x4” leads to a homogeneous microstructure with a tungsten particle size of 20-200 nm (Fig. 4b).

Fig. 4: The microstructure of the W-25%Cu after HPT to a strain of:
a) 32x2; b) 32x4

DISCUSSION

The results of this investigation clearly show that HPT can be successfully applied to fabricate nanocomposite materials. HPT of the dual phase W-Cu composite leads to a structural refinement. In comparison to the deformation of single phase materials, the plastic deformation of the dual phase W-Cu alloy has, however, some features.

- 1) The localized deformation bands appear within the material at the beginning of HPT (at strains ≤ 16). This can be explained by the strong plastic mismatch of the constituents and the inhomogeneity of the initial tungsten particle distribution in the copper matrix (Fig. 1) resulting in strong stress redistribution within the material [7].
- 2) The size of the tungsten particle size in the W-Cu composite reaches a saturation at very large strain. This behaviour seems to be similar to the grain refinement of the single phase materials [5, 8-10], however, the necessary strain to reach a saturation is significantly larger.
- 3) The fragmentation process strongly depends on the character of HPT.

The latter point seems to be especially interesting. It is clearly demonstrated that the fragmentation can be accelerated by a change of shear direction during HPT. What might be an explanation for that? As well known, in composite materials, the stress state in the constituent phases are significantly differed due to a great difference of mechanical properties of these phases. The mean field theory has been widely used to estimate the local stress states in constituent phases of composite materials from the homogeneous far-field stress field [11]. As was demonstrated in [11], the stress state in the reinforcements strongly depends on the mechanical properties of the phases, the shape of particles, and their orientation with respect to the applied far field stress tensor. From our micrographs, it is clearly seen that the tungsten particles are elongated and change their orientation with respect to the applied far field stress during HPT. Therefore, the maximum principal stress (which is, actually, a function of the mentioned above parameters) changes and reaches the fracture strength of the tungsten as a tungsten fragmentation is observed in the material during HPT. This is a continuous process. However, a change of the deformation direction of shear to the opposite, leads to abrupt change of the stresses in particles. From results of our investigations (Figs. 3d and 4a), it seems that this results in a strong increase of the maximum principal stress in tungsten particles and, as a result, in an acceleration of the tungsten fragmentation.

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